

THE PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION IN THE
PROCESS OF EDUCATION AND EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article is about the place, importance of information in the process of education and training, and information about the information system and about the collection, transmission and processing of information about the facility that provides its employees with various information to implement its management function. data is provided.

Key words: information system, technology, optical discs, technological processes, teleconferences, son'i intelligence, email mail.

The information system is a communication system for the collection, transfer and processing of information about the object that provides its employees with various information for the implementation of the management function.

The application of information systems is not only due to the processing and storage of small information, automation of writing and drawing, but also decision-making (artificial intelligence methods, expert systems, etc.), modern means of telecommunication (e-mail, teleconferences), general and in the use of local computer networks and others, it is carried out for the purpose of increasing the efficiency of the company's production and economic activity at the expense of new methods of management based on the modeling of the behavior of the company's specialists.

Depending on the degree of automation, there are manual, automated and automatic information systems. In a manual information system, some of the management or data processing functions are performed automatically, while others are performed by humans. In an automatic information system - all functions of management and data processing are performed by technical means without human intervention (for example, automatic control of technological processes).

Depending on the field of application, information systems can be divided into the following classes:

- scientific research;
- design automation;
- organizational management;

- management of technological processes.

Studying the transformation of information into knowledge is of great importance in understanding the nature of the information environment. At first glance, they seem to be the same, but in a deeper study of their relationship, we see that information has a communicative "connection between other means" of knowledge.

In society, the communication factor between people, the "bridge" between knowledge is information. Therefore, the mechanism of turning knowledge into information "for myself" (and vice versa) occupies a special place in creating an informational environment.

In ancient times, the information environment was very poor, it consisted of the most necessary and limited set of information in a narrow range, which limited the scope of communication between people for a thousand years and reduced the contribution of a person to the information environment of society.

Today, the complex of social information in various forms is wide and developed, and its role in society is incomparable.

The information environment has undergone major changes in recent times. These changes have created the need for paperless technology. This, in turn, led to the further development of the Electronic Computing Machine.

In the future, the role and importance of the information environment in human life is much higher than it is today, and it is necessary to expand the scope of the tasks to be performed. It was agreed to call this set of tasks informatization (information). The meaning of this is to reconstruct, develop and improve the efficiency of social activities based on modern Electronic Computing Machine and information system.

The purpose of information technologies is to produce information for human analysis and to make a decision on performing an action based on it.

If computerization includes technical problems, then informatization is a complex process that covers all aspects of society's life, and computers are only its technical basis. With the introduction of informatization in our republic, every citizen in it has the opportunity to get the necessary information at the right time, in the right amount, and in the right quality. Enterprises, organizations and institutions belonging to regions, cities, districts in our republic are equipped with modern computer equipment, and they are able to transmit and receive information with the help of special devices (telephone network, modem, etc.).

Therefore, informatization is not a temporary event, it is a necessary means of development, and the state of the current level of development of the information environment cannot be maintained without informatics.

It is being assured that the service of computer technology is incomparable in the performance of tasks such as fast, high-quality collection, storage, processing and transmission of information.

The independence of our republic and its increasing reputation in the world community, and because of this, the positive solution of the issue of information exchange not only within our country, but also with other countries in the world, this information is aimed at improving the economic and social condition of our republic.

The information system is defined according to the following characteristics:

- any information system can be analyzed, built and managed based on the general principles of system structure;
- the information system is dynamic and developing;
- it should be accepted as a "human-computer" system of information processing in the information system.

Information is a resource consumed by all sectors of the economy and is as important as energy or mineral resources. As the society develops, the organization of the use of the available information and information reserves about various issues such as economy, science, technology, technology, culture, art, and medicine has an increasing influence on the intellectual and economic life.

Information is a collection of scientific and technical information and knowledge about the results of science and technology development. In other words, information, according to this interpretation, is a characteristic and "commodity" of scientific and technical activity of the information service system.

Information is a set of products that form scientific and technical activities in information service systems and personnel training in various fields, that is, the production and consumption of information resources is limited only by the intellectual life of society.

It seems that the first of these interpretations gives the most complete, comprehensive understanding of information processes. Indeed, information is entering all spheres of society and human activity.

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